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**INDUSTRIAL DESIGNERS AND ENGINEERS IN
PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT**
CONFLICTS AND APPROACHES FOR IMPROVING COLLABORATION

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ABSTRACT

This survey analyzes the complex reasons for conflicts in collaboration of industrial designers and engineers in the context of product development. By qualitative interviews developers in the industrial practice were asked for their personal perception of attitude and behavior in cooperation. In addition, findings of psychological research regarding conflicts, diversity in cross-functional teams were transferred to understand conflicts in the regarded area of tense. Based on these findings opportunities for improving the cooperation were developed, mainly in the field of team leadership, process planning and education.

Keywords: industrial design engineering, cross-functional team, conflict.

INTRODUCTION

The development of successful products in global markets demands a good collaboration of industrial designers and engineers to realize an efficient and aesthetic result (Kranke 2008). However, the cooperation is often affected by misunderstandings, prejudices and conflicts between two disciplines that need to assert themselves in a similar context. While the problem itself is known, its complex reasons have not yet been gathered and analyzed as a whole. The goal of this research study was to detect the potential for conflicts in industrial practice with a focus on personal attitude and behavior. Most of the figures in this survey compare the two disciplines. For an easier understanding all elements related to engineering are blue, those related to industrial design are illustrated in red.

TERMINOLOGY

Development Disciplines

The study relates to the professional categories of engineer and industrial designers in Germany, especially in the field of investment goods. Mentioning **engineers** stands for graduates in mechanical engineering, in particular in the field of product development. Here the cooperation with industrial designers is most common. It is equivalent to the term «engineering designer». Talking about **industrial designers** means graduates in product design mostly from a university of applied science working in a product development department for investment goods.

Figure 1. Mechanical engineer (author) and industrial designer (Konstantin Grcic).

Diversity

Diversity refers to differences between individuals on any attribute that may lead to the perception that another person is different from self (van Knippenberg et al. 2004). It refers to a large number of dimensions like religion and nationality. Regarding this survey the work-group diversity is primarily relevant. It may have positive and negative effects on group performance (van Knippenberg et al. 2004).

The higher performance of a diverse team due to multiple perspectives, abilities and opinions appearing in constructive task conflicts is a positive aspect. A negative impact of diversity can occur, when a social categorization happens leading to less group cohesion and thereby to relationship conflicts (William & O'Reilly 1998).

Conflict

Usable is a categorization of conflicts in three types: relationship, task and process conflict (Jehn & Mannix 2001). **Relationship conflicts** arise from interpersonal incompatibilities including affective components such as feeling tension and friction. These conflicts are always detrimental to individual and group performance as well as to member satisfaction. **Task conflicts** are disputes about work contents due to different viewpoints and opinions. A moderate level of task conflicts can be beneficial to group performance, in particular for complex cognitive tasks. In **process conflicts** members disagree about how and when certain task accomplishment will proceed within a development process. They pertain to issues of duty and resource delegation and therefore should arise and be resolved in the beginning of a project.

Cross-functional team

Groups with members of different scientific disciplines or different business units are called cross-functional teams. The collaboration of diverse experts shall obtain innovative results, though the effort to coordinate cross-functional teams is much higher than in homogeneous groups.

HYPOTHESES

Continuum of development disciplines

There is a variety of developers in each discipline. In practice the variety in the other discipline is not perceived. That leads to stereotypes and thereby to conflicts.

Very important for analyzing conflicts in development teams is having a closer view on the two disciplines. There is a large bandwidth of professions in product development and engineering design (Lindemann 2005). Regarding their

collaboration the two examined disciplines can be arranged as shown in figure 2. The continuum of engineers ranges from the «calculator» as a pure technical developer to the interdisciplinary oriented «product developer» with interest and knowledge in user-related issues like aesthetics or usability. In between these two extreme characteristics there is a wide variety of engineers. On the other side industrial designers are arranged similarly. «Artists» mainly attend to shape and aesthetics while a «product developer» is an industrial designer dealing with engineering issues as well.

Figure 2. Spectrum of mechanical engineers and industrial designers with possible interpersonal conflicts.

In practice a problem herewith can be observed: Developers often perceive colleagues of the other discipline in a reduced and stereotypical characteristic. Many engineers see industrial designers just as «artists» while most of these think that every engineer is a kind of «calculator» without any creativity. As a result conflicts due to wrong expectations arise.

Relevance of relationship conflicts

The impact of interpersonal conflicts in interdisciplinary teams is stronger than the effect due to the lack of task-related methods and design approaches.

Respecting the different characteristics of developers several conflicts in between can occur as shown in figure 2. Literature in the area of tense of industrial design engineering often deals with methods and processes to overcome task related problems. However, cohesion and a positive mood in the interdisciplinary team are much more relevant

for group performance as thereby relationship conflicts can easily be degraded. These aspects are seldom treated in the relevant literature.

Power struggle due to the lack of team briefing

An insufficient briefing without dealing with responsibilities and goals leads to power struggles in a late stage of the project and thereby to huge losses concerning efficiency.

A briefing is the first generative step in the development process and influences the result remarkably (Goos & Zang 2009). However, only 40% of asked developers in their survey declared to have an interdisciplinary design briefing in the beginning of the project. Tuckman (1965) identifies four stages in group development: The **forming** stage with testing and dependence, the **storming** phase with intragroup conflicts, in the **norming** phase new standards and structures are set and finally the **performing** stage, in which a group works efficiently. Without a collective briefing in the beginning of a development process arranging roles, tasks and structures power struggles, relationship conflicts and destructive process conflicts occur in a moment when the group should rather perform.

LITERATURE FINDINGS

DEFICIT IN RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY

In spite of the awareness for problems in the surveyed area of tense, only little specific literature dealing with methodical integration of design issues in product development processes is available. Moreover these approaches are of a rather theoretical nature (Goos & Zang 2009). Primarily in the field of industrial design a lack of scientific research and methodology can be observed. As a consequence the job outline and core competencies of industrial designers are mostly vague.

INTERDISCIPLINARY PRODUCT BRIEFING

In their observant survey of medium-sized enterprises Goos & Zang (2009) noticed that often engineering related briefings and those for industrial designers do not overlap. Although working on the same project developers of different disciplines have unequal information. An inadequate briefing can

lead to poor communication, deficient flow of information and permanently changing project requirements (Goos & Zang 2009). In particular cross-functional teams demand a superior management as it is hard to provide accepted shared goals for members of different disciplines (Ehrlenspiel 2007).

INTEGRATED PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

Interdisciplinary development processes to support the collaboration are rarely implemented in practice. While engineers have many design approaches available, industrial designers orient themselves less commonly by means of given models. In the survey of Goos & Zang (2009) only 55% of industrial designers stated using a default proceeding. For this reason the authors propose the five-stages-process for integrated concept development as shown in the «approaches for improving collaboration».

INTERDISCIPLINARY EDUCATION

Another deficit can be observed related to education: In most educational engineering the teaching of contents of industrial design are completely missing. Graduates have no clear perception of their prospective colleagues. On the other hand a focus in the education of industrial design students is mostly missing. Dealing with a broad range of disciplines, they have difficulties distinguishing core abilities and superficial knowledge. The Bayern Design GmbH (2004) surveyed German design education and delivered a «destructive» judgment: fragmentary integration of other disciplines, deficient computer skills and a lack of practical relevance. Universities which impart interdisciplinary competencies are very rare.

COMMUNICATION

Great problems in collaboration result from communication issues. Different mental models of industrial designers and engineers downgrade information processes by «representational gaps» (Cronin & Weingart 2007). They use similar terms with different meanings. This can lead to miscomprehensions which have a worse impact than a complete lack of understanding as they are hard to notice and their consequences arise very late. Communication problems also occur when developers

use their specific terminology deliberately to escape critical questions or comments.

RESEARCH METHOD

For testing the hypotheses **qualitative interviews** with developers of both disciplines were conducted in industrial practice. 10 engineers and 7 industrial designers in field of investment goods were interviewed. Precondition for the selection of enterprises was the feasibility to run interviews with developers of both disciplines being in a direct cooperation. The questions are shown in figure 3.

Personal Data

1. Date 2. Education

3. Branch 4. Activity

Situation analysis

5. How often do you deal with an engineer?

6. How strong do you estimate the impact of engineers on the developed product?
 low rather low rather high high

7. How strong do you estimate your own impact on the developed product?
 low rather low rather high high

8. How do you judge the quality of results achieved by your collaboration?
 bad rather bad rather good good n/a

9. How do you judge the atmosphere in collaboration?
 bad rather bad rather good good n/a

Questions towards attitude

10. What does work well in collaboration? What does not work well?
 11. How strong do you estimate the impact of conflicts on product quality?
 12. In which way have collaboration and conflicts changed in the last years?
 13. Which activities should engineers perform more, which less?
 14. Which activities should you as an industrial designer perform more, which less?
 15. Which core competencies do engineers have, which ones industrial designers?
 16. Which development process do you use? Does it support the collaboration?
 17. How could the coordination and organization of your collaboration be improved?
 18. What do you like engineers to change to improve your collaboration?
 19. What could you as an industrial designer change to improve collaboration?

Figure 3. Excerpt from the questionnaire for industrial designers.

The qualitative parts of the interviews were recorded and transliterated. The duration of the 22 interviews averaged 34 minutes. Afterwards the statements were summarized, explicated and structured as described in Mayring (2008). The results of this proceeding are treated and structured in the discussion.

In addition to questions regarding their relationship to and cooperation with other developers the developers were asked to define their self-perception and perception concerning colleagues. The evaluation of this **quantitative part** of the survey is illustrated in the tables 1 and 2.

With the qualitative part of the questions altogether 5 researchers in the field of industrial design, mechanical engineering and psychology were interviewed. In contrast to the subjective statements of developers, these experts should describe the area of tense on a meta-level.

RESULTS OF QUANTITATIVE PART

In the quantitative part of the survey a task regarding perception was carried out by the participants. The developers should agree or disagree with different roles of both disciplines, for example «the engineer as generalist» or «the industrial designer as artist». Table 1 shows the results concerning the perception of industrial designers, table 2 regarding engineers.

Table 1. Role models of industrial designers judged by engineers and in self-perception.

ROLE MODELS OF INDUSTRIAL DESIGNERS

In their self-perception **industrial designers** judged themselves mainly as «product gestalter», «concept developer», «advocate of user», «visionary» and «generalist». They rather rejected their role model as «artist» and «stylist». **Engineers** confirmed their role model as «product gestalter» and «visionary». Comparing the valuation of both perceptions some

divergences are noticeable. Industrial designers saw themselves stronger as «concept developer», «advocate of user» and «moderators» compared to engineers, who assessed them rather as «artist» and «stylist» in contrast to their self-perception.

Table 2. Role models of engineers judged by industrial designers and in self-perception.

ROLE MODELS OF ENGINEERS

The other way around engineers perceived themselves as «constructing engineer», «product developer», «optimizer» and «specialist» and refused their role model as members of the «won't-work-club» rejecting all new ideas of other developers with the comment: That won't work! Industrial designers also saw engineers as «constructing engineers» and «specialists» but rather rejected their role model as «product gestalter», «craftsmen» and «visionary». In comparison engineers judged themselves more as «product gestalter», «craftsmen», «concept developer», «visionary» and «generalist» than industrial designers, who had a stronger perception of engineers as members in the «won't-work-club» than those had in self-perception.

DISCUSSION

ROLE MODELS

Conflicts often arise in different views concerning role models (Goos & Zang 2009). The survey has shown that many developers have false expectation of competencies or tasks relating to other disciplines. Moreover, engineers sometimes don't know at all what industrial designers do, like the following statements of engineers show: «I know that designers make pretty curves, but beyond that I don't know what they do», «Being honest, I actually have no idea about a designers' approach or about his abilities», «I don't know what the difference between designer and stylist is».

The assumption that engineers see industrial designers as artists or stylists was not confirmed although their estimation is higher than in self-perception of industrial designers.

A strong potential for conflicts lies in the task of concept development as both disciplines judged themselves stronger than the other one. The assignment of tasks for that should already be discussed during a briefing in the beginning.

Moreover, engineers overestimate themselves as product gestalter. Most of the asked engineers were convinced to be able to create or at least judge the formal aesthetic aspects of a product. Thereby it is not bad at all to make proposition concerning embodiment design as an engineers. Also industrial designers confess that engineers can learn a lot and make good proposals. But they should be aware of not being educated in aesthetics design as industrial designer and not to overestimate themselves.

The same problem occurs regarding the role model of industrial designers as generalists: It is necessary for them to have a broad knowledge of many disciplines but they should also not overestimate their ability and see themselves as experts in a field they are not educated in. According to that Peters (2004) is talking in his dissertation of the difference between ability (German: «können») and knowing (German: «kennen»). The most important aspect of being a generalist is to understand the language of other disciplines and to know whom to ask.

RESPONSIBILITY AND LIABILITY

One explanation for the role model of engineers as members of the «won't-work-club» is the responsibility due to liability of engineers for their products. In most cases industrial designers do not attend the development of a product until its manufacturing. For this reason they can hardly be held responsible for failures of completed products. In contrast engineers stick to validated methods and proceedings and are in favor of rejecting new ideas, at least by reason of self-protection. Finally this difference must be seen as an advantage of interdisciplinary teams: Industrial designers get away with being more open-minded and taking risks, whereby the possibility to create an innovation is higher. By contrast to this «dreaming», engineers as «realizers» are also important. It is important to have a balanced mixture and once again to be aware of the different role models and the reasons for that.

TEAM BRIEFING

In the qualitative part of the interview developers of both disciplines mentioned the importance of involving other members in the development process in an early stage. This implies that both, engineers and industrial designers, think that they are the «leading» person in the process deciding when to involve whom. However, the required competencies depend on the character of the developed product. In few interviews developers mentioned that it is important to involve all disciplines in equal parts to the whole project, but this general claim does not fit to different types of products. Sometimes it can be justified to involve engineers or industrial designers only for a short while. According to all surveyed experts it is essential to have, independent of the product type, a collective briefing with all involved disciplines to generate a shared understanding of project goals. Goos & Zang (2009) propose a set of relevant aspects for a «product briefing». However, questions concerning the team constellation, handling of team members and conflicts are missing in most briefings. Therefore, an extension of product briefings by adding allocations of responsibilities and interpersonal issues appears reasonable to anticipate process conflicts and to avoid relationship conflicts; hence the «product briefing» should be extended to a «team briefing».

LEADERSHIP

The requirements for a leader of interdisciplinary teams are high: In particular in his role as a moderator a leader should be able to communicate with and understand the contents and tasks of all involved disciplines. Furthermore, the leader has to create a shared understanding of goals and rules within his team as described in the discussion of team briefing. Only that way, synergies of interdisciplinary teams overbalance the coordination efforts and emerging conflicts. Beyond that the interdisciplinary team must be led like any other team: Ehrlenspiel (1995) postulates a reasonable size of less than eight members to prevent inefficiency, a good moderation, the right team constellation and clear goals. Furthermore the surveyed psychologist suggests «transformational leadership» to create an atmosphere of faith, respect, loyalty and appreciation towards the leader and to motivate members with a vision.

COMMUNICATION

A good understanding of engineers and industrial designers within a team is the basis for advantages of collaboration. At the same time it is impossible and also undesirable to learn the language and the way of thinking of the other discipline as a whole. Important is the shared understanding of goals and the awareness of developers that their colleagues could not understand statements. To prevent «representational gaps», as described in the literature findings of communication, important agreements should be paraphrased by all disciplines to ensure their common understanding. Many surveyed developers and experts mentioned a difference of character comparing engineers and industrial designers, which has an impact on communication: Engineers are rather introverted, while industrial designers are more extroverted. An expert in this field stresses that engineers often have problems to express themselves and to embody emotions and wishes regarding the impression of a product. At last an industrial designer in a leading position expressed a wish concerning communication for all developers: «Listen more, speak less».

DRAFTING TECHNIQUES

A controversial issue is the use of different drafting techniques like hand sketching and CAD. Engineers often criticize the susceptibility to manipulate hand sketches due to high abilities of industrial designers. Thereby they can illustrate «impossible» products that look nice but are not realizable. Even some industrial designers confess that they sometimes sensibly belie problems of a concepts' feasibility by hand sketches. At the same time engineers seldom dare to sketch their ideas themselves because they feel unpleasant and insecure next to an industrial designer, whose skills to illustrate as a «professional» are much higher. For this reason many engineers turn to CAD models in an early stage, at which hand sketches would be much more effective. Furthermore they restrict their possibilities to the tools offered by CAD systems.

Therefore, engineers should train their abilities in hand sketching to at least express rough ideas. At the same time industrial designers should not be misled by the freedoms of hand sketches. They should be able to prove their propositions in a CAD system. Most engineers claim from designers to have the ability to generate their proposed complex surfaces in CAD, as it is hard to please the demands of them in a CAD model on the basis of a rough designers' scribble.

HYPOTHESES TESTING

The bandwidth of different developers of both disciplines described in the hypothesis of **continuum of development disciplines** proved true. At the same time the perception of engineers as «calculators» and industrial designers as «artist» or «stylists» was not noticeable. However, divergences between perceptions of role models were observable leading to conflicts. Remarkable was the partially discoverable ignorance of skills and tasks concerning the other discipline, in particular by engineers. Conflicts in such development teams do not appear unlikely.

Regarding the **relevance of relationship conflicts** in particular literature in the field of organizational psychology provided evidences: Jehn & Mannix (2010) detected that relationship conflicts are harmful to group performance and the satisfaction of members. Fearfulness due to interpersonal animosities hinders cognitive functions and diverts from tasks leading to less efficiency. Moreover, there is a correlation between relationship and task conflicts. Relationship conflicts can become manifest in destructive task conflicts. Accordingly, high attention must be spent to relationships and atmosphere, especially in an interdisciplinary development team.

The importance of a team briefing in the beginning of a development project was also proved. **Power struggle due to the lack of team briefing** lead to destructive process conflicts (Jehn & Mannix 2010) in

Figure 4. Characteristic drafting tools and work environments of engineers and industrial designers.

a belated stage of the project, when much work is already done. Several developers reported of projects in which different disciplines were mixed without setting clear rules or goals. As a result every developer worked on his own behalf and mostly these projects turned to flops. Struggles between developers occurred, as everyone wanted to «win» and assert his idea. Without a shared understanding of goals no synergy effects could be deployed.

APPROACHES FOR IMPROVING COLLABORATION

For minimizing problem potentials several actions must be taken: Great importance must be attached to the **management** of an interdisciplinary team. Ideally a leader possesses abilities and experience in both disciplines and is able to communicate properly with all members of his team. An extensive **team briefing** with all included members discussing product issues as well as rules of cooperation is indispensable in the beginning of a project. There is a large amount of **design approaches** to coordinate a development process with participation of engineers and industrial designers, although they are seldom used in practice. An example for that is the five-stages-model by Goos & Zang (2009) in figure 5.

Figure 5. Five-stages-process for integrated concept development adapted by Goos & Zang (2009).

A high potential for practical support of the collaboration appears in interdisciplinary **methodology**. While many methods in engineering design exist and are used, a lot of industrial

designers fear being disturbed in their creativity when they use systematic approaches. Methods that cover issues of both disciplines and support their communication would be helpful.

Not least for the development of those methods, but also for a better understanding of problems in practice, an improvement of **scientific research** in «industrial design engineering» and thereby of **education** in this area of tense could help to reduce conflicts in practice.

Finally one interviewed industrial designer mentioned the best condition for a good collaboration: He established **enthusiasm, pride and identification** toward the embodiment design among the engineers in his company. Engineers who like the embodiment design are highly motivated for a good collaboration and do everything to realize the design proposals. The phenomenon of «won't-work-club» does not exist at all. Gaining design awards can help to reach this condition.

CONCLUSION & OUTLOOK

Most of the surveyed developers underlined the importance of a successful collaboration of engineering and industrial design to fulfill demands towards products in a global market. The research study showed that conflicts in interdisciplinary teams have various complex reasons. Beside the organization of the collaboration mainly psychological aspects like personal attitudes and prejudices but also the ignorance of activities and competencies of other developers influence the quality of the outcome. These attitudes are already developed during the education and mostly hard to overcome when the first contact to other disciplines is made in industrial practice. Universities and enterprises must notice this fact to avoid prospective conflicts. A strong management with an experienced leader of interdisciplinary teams is necessary to overcome these difficulties.

The interviews in this study were run with relatively few developers in a qualitative conduction. Based on this study a **quantitative survey** with a larger amount of developers could enlarge the understanding of practical problems of interdisciplinary teams. In addition a high potential is seen in research findings in the field of

organizational psychology and in adapting them to the product development context.

As mentioned in the discussion a **team briefing** which includes practical project goal as well as agreements regarding interpersonal collaboration

and the handling of different conflicts would improve the cooperation of interdisciplinary development teams. It is necessary to generate tangible contents of a team briefing integrating task and relational issues in the range of industrial design engineering.

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